

Rice market integration in Bangladesh

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Rice is the main source of protein and calorie intake in Bangladesh, contributing 93% of the total food-grain supply. The government liberalized the food grain sector in 1992 to ensure food and nutritional security. Policy instruments included removing controls, eliminating food subsidies, allowing private traders to import/export grains, and withdrawing restrictions on both domestic and international trade. The extent to which the rice market is integrated is fundamental to achieving policy objectives.

This study examines rice market integration in Bangladesh from 1992 to 1997. Following Baffes (1991), the law of one price (LOP) was used to test spatial market integration using cointegration analysis. Our testing procedure is as follows. For the LOP to hold between prices in any two markets, prices must be cointegrated. This means that their difference must be stationary, with a constant mean, a constant variance, and a constant covariance between any two observations. A necessary, but not sufficient, condition for cointegration is that each series must be integrated of the same order. First order integration I (1) is called a unit root and implies that the series is stationary in first differences.

Bangladesh has four main city markets for rice—Dhaka, Chittagong, Rajshahi,

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Dhaka	Chittagong
Mymensingh	Noakhali
Jamalpur	Comilla
Tangail	Sylhet
Faridpur	Chittagong Hill Tracts
Rajshahi	Khulna
Rangpur	Jessor
Dinajpur	Kustia
Bogra	Barisal
Pabna	

and Khulna—and we divided the country into four regions centered on each. The table shows associated markets. Nominal monthly average wholesale coarse rice prices from January 1992 to December 1997 for these 19 markets were examined. We tested for market integration by testing for the LOP first between each market in each region and second between the main city markets.

In the first stage, we tested for unit roots in each series using the Dickey-Fuller test (Dickey and Fuller 1981). All were I (1) except for that in Barisal, which was excluded from further analysis. In the second stage, we tested for stationarity in the difference between each pairwise price again using the Dickey-Fuller test and all were stationary. Thus, pairwise prices were cointegrated and the LOP held universally.

We have three main results. First, the rice price in each city market was cointegrated with prices in other city markets. Second, the price in each city market was cointegrated with prices in associated markets. Third, each market in each region was cointegrated with all other markets in the same region, except for Barisal in the Khulna region. Thus, with the exception of Barisal, all markets in all regions were cointegrated by extension, and the LOP held. In contrast, the Barisal market appeared segmented, possibly because of geographical isolation.

In conclusion, following the liberalization and privatization of the food-grain sector in Bangladesh in 1992, rice markets were integrated. The government can therefore rely on market forces to supply food to deficit regions from regions producing a surplus. Moreover, its food policy, which aims to achieve the goals of food and nutritional security, appears efficient.

References

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The International Rice Functional Genomics Working Group

To facilitate collaboration and transfer of new findings from genomic research to applications, IRRI organized the International Rice Functional Genomics Working Group. The Working Group has the following objectives:

- Build a research community with a shared vision on rice functional genomics
- Create a common resource platform to broaden access to new knowledge and tools in functional genomics

- Accelerate application of functional genomics to rice improvement

The Working Group is intended to be a broad-based collaborative network that will benefit participants by pooling expertise and resources. To date, several institutions have expressed interest to participate in this working group.

Through a series of meetings and consultations, three activities that are considered high priority by the rice research community were identified:

1. Create an information node to communicate information related to functional genomics

2. Promote the sharing of genetic stocks
3. Facilitate sharing of resources for microarray analysis

A Web-based information node was established as an entry point for finding and sharing information and providing links to individual laboratories or organizations with interest in rice functional genomics. For more information about the site and the Working Group, go to: <http://www.cgiar.org/irri/>

To send comments, inputs, and suggestions, write or e-mail: genomics@irri.exch.cgiar.org